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ABSTRACT

One of the main objectives of the PowerMat work-package is the development and characterization of novel and advanced materials for demanding thermal management applications and high-energy particle accelerators. In this document, we present the comprehensive characterization campaigns performed at CERN, GSI and Polimi on a broad spectrum of advanced materials, including recent grades of Molybdenum Carbide – Graphite (MoGr), Thermal Pyrolytic Graphite (TPG), several grades of Carbon Fibre reinforced Carbon (CFC), Isotropic Graphites, Carbon Foams, Glassy Carbon (GC), Copper – Diamond (CuCD), with and without thin-film coatings.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

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Executive summary

In this report, an extensive characterization campaign of a broad range of advanced materials, based on carbon allotropes, for applications in future particle accelerators was presented. These materials comprise both novel materials, currently under development, as Molybdenum Carbide – Graphite (MoGr) and Copper – Diamond (CuCD), as well as commercially available graphitic materials, also including thin-film coatings. This campaign permitted to identify a number of improvements and optimization steps to be implemented in the production processes, with additional measurements to be performed soon.

Microstructures analyses performed at CERN by SEM and XRD techniques evidenced that the addition of small amounts of titanium to MoGr stabilizes at room temperature a phase, which, in undoped carbides, is stable only at very high temperature. The highly oriented structure of Thermal Pyrolytic Graphite (TPG) was confirmed, evidencing a strong electron channelling effect through material basal planes.

Thermophysical and mechanical properties of several MoGr grades, CuCD and TPG were measured at CERN. This characterization confirmed the advantages of MoGr compared to commercially available materials as TPG, when used in accelerator equipment subjected to thermal and mechanical loads, for its better-balanced properties. CuCD is even more mechanically resistant than MoGr; however, its higher density and lower heat transport properties advocate its use in components with lower particle energy deposition.

At GSI, investigations were performed on a wide range of commercially available advanced graphitic materials: these included several isotropic graphite grades, 2D ex-PAN CFC grades, a 3D ex-PAN CFC, graphitic foams, glassy carbon and TPG.

Investigation techniques included Raman spectroscopy, temperature-depending laser flash analysis, micro-indentation and three point bending tests.

Raman spectroscopy evidenced the lowest graphitic defect concentration in carbon foams and, even more, in TPG, while largest defects were found in Glassy Carbon. Elastic properties measured by micro-indentation appeared rather low compared to macroscopic measurements, particularly for anisotropic materials: this inconsistency should be further investigated.

UHV performance were measured at CERN on samples of MoGr and CuCD. Tested MoGr grades were found to have an outgassing rate higher than other graphitic materials used in BID. The main reason for this difference was conjectured and additional developments and tests are shortly foreseen.

The gas analysis revealed a high mass contamination affecting the UHV behaviour of CuCD. This shall be eliminated at the source, with a proper handling of the material and by controlling the cleanliness of the production process.

At Polimi, a methodology was developed to thermomechanically characterize coatings by the combined use of Brillouin Spectroscopy (BS) and Substrate Curvature (SC) techniques, in a complete non-destructive way. The roughness of Carbon/Carbon and MoGr samples coated with molybdenum

did not allow to apply this method straightforwardly. However, a number of countermeasures were identified and should allow to overcome this limitation in future investigations.

1. Introduction

The development and use of high thermal performance materials, with low mass density and excellent resistance to thermal shock, has become an enabling technology in a broad range of industrial and research applications. In industry, these materials are appealing in a number of high technology fields, such as high power electronics, avionics, energy production, aerospace, nuclear engineering, high performance automotive, where efficient thermal management, high temperature resistance and mechanical robustness are desired.

These requirements are largely shared with the so-called beam intercepting devices (BID), such as collimators, beam absorbers, catchers, dumps and targets, used in high-energy particle accelerators: these pieces of equipment are exposed to deliberate or accidental impacts of highly energetic and intense particle beams, making the selection of compliant materials extremely delicate.

Carbon-based materials have a long history of applications in BID and their harsh radiation environments, as they exhibit low activation, high radiation-hardness, thermal stability in combination with improved strength at high temperatures and low density. The next-generation of accelerator facilities like the High-Luminosity upgrade of LHC (HL-LHC) [1], the Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research (FAIR) [2], or the proposed Future Circular Collider (FCC) [3] will have increased beam intensities (by orders of magnitude); in combination with decreasing pulse lengths requested by physics experiments, this leads to significantly higher transient thermo-mechanical loads in all BID. Additionally, materials for some BID must possess high electric conductivity to limit the destabilizing effects they may induce on particle beams circulating in their close vicinity: this is for instance the case of the active parts of collimators for the LHC and the HL-LHC.

In order to assess the suitability of various advanced engineered materials and gain a deeper understanding of their response to beam-induced dynamic thermal stresses, dedicated experiments are needed at facilities like CERN's High-Radiation to Materials (HiRadMat), GSI's UNILAC and SIS100 accelerators, with short-pulse, high-intensity beams.

Unfortunately, no existing material possesses the combination of physical, thermal, electrical and mechanical properties, imposed by such extreme working conditions.

To meet these demands, a comprehensive research has been launched at CERN in collaboration with international laboratories, universities and industries, focusing on the exploration of advanced types of carbons, such as pyrolytic graphite, carbon foams and new carbon/carbon composites, and on the development of novel composite materials based on the combination of carbon allotropes (i.e. graphite and diamond) with metals or high performance ceramics. After having commenced in the framework of EuCARD [1] and EuCARD-2 [5] projects, these activities are continuing within ARIES collaboration, Work Package 17 (PowerMat) Joint Research Activity.

In the 12 months, WP17 partners completed an extensive characterization of composites under development, such as Molybdenum Carbide – Graphite (MoGr) and Copper – Diamond (CuCD), along with commercially available carbon-based materials, such as various grades of isotropic graphite, thermal pyrolytic graphite, carbon-fibre-reinforced carbon (CFC) and carbon foams. The characterization performed included the study of materials morphology and microstructure, the measurement of their thermal, electrical and mechanical properties, as well as their behaviour in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) and the study of application of thin films on the surfaces of the bulk materials.

This campaign has allowed quantifying the advantages of novel composites, compared to commercial materials and has laid the ground for further optimizations and improvements in the development of advanced thermal management materials. It will be complemented in the course of the projects by additional characterization campaigns, including examination after long-term irradiation and experiments under high intensity particle pulses. Results of this thorough characterization are reported in the next chapters.

2. Overview of investigated materials

Materials presented in this report were developed or procured to respond to the more challenging requirements posed by BID intended to be installed in future high-energy accelerators such as HL-LHC, FAIR or FCC.

For instance, the material currently employed for the absorbers of LHC Collimator jaws (a two-dimensional Carbon-Carbon composite) [6] is predicted not to satisfy the full set of requirements imposed by the severe working conditions expected in the HL-LHC from 2026: in particular, numerical simulations indicate that the limited electrical conductivity of CFC may induce electromagnetic instabilities in the particle beam.

In this context, a family of graphite-matrix composites, reinforced with molybdenum carbides (Molybdenum Carbide – Graphite, MoGr) was co-developed by CERN and Brevetti Bizz (IT) [7], with the goal of increasing the electrical conductivity of the materials for the primary and secondary collimator jaws, while maintaining or improving the beam impact robustness of CFC [8]. A beam-impact experiment performed in 2015 (HRMT-23) at the CERN HiRadMat facility [9] demonstrated the validity of the design of HL-LHC secondary collimators with MoGr (grade MG-6530Aa) absorbers. Further material developments have occurred since the HRMT-23 experiment and a new grade with improved properties (MG-6403Fc) was chosen for manufacturing a collimator prototype that is being tested in the LHC ring. This grade was then also tested in HiRadMat, in 2017, in an experiment named “Multimat” [10]: the material survived to proton impacts having energy densities exceeding the ones expected in HL-LHC.

To further increase the electrical conductivity of the jaw surface exposed to the beam, a thin film of electrically conductive metals or ceramics can be applied to the MoGr bulk material. Solutions under development are, for example, molybdenum, copper and titanium nitride coatings.

On the other hand, Copper-Diamond (CuCD), produced by RHP Technology (AT), is proposed as an upgrade of the tungsten heavy alloy currently adopted in tertiary collimators. The material is, in fact, much more robust to proton beam impacts. This was also confirmed by the two HiRadMat experiments mentioned above.

Other commercially available carbon materials were considered for BID after an extensive market survey. Carbon-based materials exist in a large variety due to their very broad applications domains, like electrodes for electric discharge, aluminium furnaces, moulds for glass forming, heaters and crucibles for crystal growing in semiconductor industry, electric brushes, airplane and high-end automotive brakes or rocket exhaust nozzles, high-temperature furnace cladding, inert containers for corrosive agents, high-temperature gaskets or seals and heat sinks for high-power electronics.

The studied materials include several isotropic polycrystalline graphite grades (PG) from POCO Entegris and SGL Carbon, 2D Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-fibre reinforced CFC from SGL Carbon, a 3D PAN-fibre reinforced CFC from ArianeGroup, graphitic foams from POCO Entegris, glassy carbon (GC) from HTW Hochttemperatur-Werkstoff, and thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG) from Momentive Performance Materials.

Some of these materials will be tested in a dedicated HiRadMat experiment, named FlexMat, expected in the coming months.

An overview of the main features of the materials characterized in the first 12 months of WP17 is provided in the next sections of this chapter.

2.1. MOLYBDENUM CARBIDE – GRAPHITE

MoGr is produced by spark plasma sintering (SPS), starting from powders of graphite, molybdenum and, in some grades, carbon fibres and titanium. SPS, a variation of hot pressing also known as Field-Assisted Sintering Technique (FAST) or Pulsed Electric Current Sintering (PECS), is a powder metallurgy technology that combines uniaxial mechanical pressure and the application of electrical current to the system. The sintered material heats up by Joule effect. The temperatures reached during the sintering, in excess of 2600°C, allow melting the molybdenum carbide formed during the process, exploiting the advantages of liquid phase sintering. Molten carbides induce catalytic graphitization by the dissolution of individual carbon atoms, eventually connecting them to form high quality solid graphite. This continuous dynamic dissolution-precipitation process dissolves the most disordered and hence most reactive carbon structures – such as amorphous regions or unconnected edges of basal planes – and precipitates ordered graphite that grows and bridges the initial graphite crystallites.

Full details of the production process are available in [8].

The intrinsic morphology of the graphite matrix and the manufacturing process lead to a transversely isotropic material: the in-plane and perpendicular directions are defined as those parallel and perpendicular to the graphite basal planes, as shown in Figure 1.

Several grades were recently developed in order to improve key thermophysical properties. The naming and initial composition of the MoGr grades tested in the framework of this project are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1 – Preferred orientation of graphite basal planes with respect to the uniaxial pressure applied during the sintering process. Naming convention for the in-plane and through-plane/perpendicular material directions.

Table 1 – Composition of tested MoGr grades

	MG-6530Aa	MG-6541Aa	MG-6403Fc	MG-6541Fc
Vol.% Molybdenum	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.4
Vol.% Graphite	90.5	90.1	94.95	90.1
Vol.% Short CF ¹	0	5	0	5
Vol.% Long CF ¹	5	0	0	0
Vol.% Titanium	0	0.5	0.55	0.5

2.2. COPPER DIAMOND

CuCD is a composite material developed with the goal of combining the main advantages of its two constituents: copper and diamond. Its thermal properties exceed those of pure copper, while diamonds strongly reduce the thermal expansion coefficient and the density of the composite with respect to the pure metal [11].

The CuCD grade presented in this report, manufactured by RHP-Technology (AT), can be produced by SPS or by conventional hot pressing, using a compact of cold pressed powders, also known as “green”, at 35 MPa. The temperature reached is slightly below the melting point of copper (1000-1050 °C), maintained for 1-4 hours, with a successive controlled cooling down to 400°C. The standard powder mixture is made of diamond particles, carbide-forming elements (*e.g.* Cr, B, Mo) and copper powder. Mono-modal and multi-modal diamond mixtures were adopted. The process is conducted under dry hydrogen gas atmosphere. Usually, the material is produced in a sandwich setup, meaning a metallic layer on the top and on the bottom, with the composite in the middle. The function of the metallic layer is to allow reaching good surface tolerances during machining. A stress relieving heat treatment at 300-400 °C for one hour may be performed after the hot pressing cycle.

2.3. COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE CARBON-BASED MATERIALS

2.3.1. THERMAL PYROLYTIC GRAPHITE

Thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG) is manufactured by Momentive Performance Materials (US) from thermal decomposition of hydrocarbon gas at high temperature [12]. It is produced by the dissociation of hydrocarbon gases in a chemical vapour deposition process. This leads to an epitaxial growth of graphene layers with only little defect concentration. The high alignment of the graphene layers enhances the thermal and electrical conductivities of the material along the basal planes. Due to the nature of strongly aligned graphite structure, the material is highly anisotropic, having very different properties in the through-plane direction, compared to the in-plane. One of the biggest drawbacks is its very low strength in the through-plane direction, that makes it extremely sensitive to cracks due to traction, bending or shear between the graphitic layers.

¹ Short carbon fibres: length 250 µm; long carbon fibres: length 3 mm

2.3.2. CARBON FOAMS

Carbon foams are low-density materials with very high porosity and a graphite matrix, in which most of the macropores (cells) are interconnected, leading to an open cell structure. They have novel features due to this cell structure, such as large geometric surface area, associated with the fundamental properties characteristic for carbon materials, such as low density, high thermal stability, hydrophobic surface nature, high thermal and electrical conductivities, and so on. Several grades are available on the market, with different levels of graphitization: the higher the graphitization degree, the better the thermal and electrical conductivities.

2.3.3. CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED CARBON COMPOSITE

Carbon fibre – Carbon (CFC) is a composite material made of a graphite matrix strengthened with carbon fibres. Several types of CFC are available, depending on the graphitization level and on the orientation and type of the carbon fibres. The grades in which fibre reinforcements are oriented in the three directions are called 3D CFC. On the other hand, when the fibres are lying on parallel planes, connected between each other by weak inter-basal bonds, materials are called 2D CFC. In 2D CFC fibres might be continuous and weaved in fabric or short and randomly oriented in the plane. Fibres might be obtained from Polyacrylonitrile (ex-PAN) or pitch (ex-pitch).

2.3.4. ISOTROPIC GRAPHITE

Isotropic graphite contains only graphite grains, randomly oriented, thus resulting in isotropic properties. The grades available on the market differ by graphitization and compaction levels.

2.3.5. GLASSY CARBON

Glassy carbon is also a material purely made out of carbon, but here the structure of the atoms is not ordered, but amorphous. This provides very different properties with respect to the other graphite-based materials, as the structure at the nanoscale level is completely different. Completely amorphous carbons lack of free electrons in the C-C bonds; they are thus electrical insulators, as opposite to graphite.

3. Microstructural observations

3.1. INTRODUCTION AND ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

A thorough microstructural characterization revealing the microscopic morphology of materials is extremely important to anticipate their behaviour under several aspects, such as phase and element compositions and their effects, degree of anisotropy, porosity and so on.

Analysis techniques used in this report include scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and ion polishing.

Microstructural analyses are performed using a Zeiss Sigma field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM). Investigated materials include MoGr, CuCD and TPG.

Scanning Electron Microscopy is an analysis technique that relies on an accelerated electron beam as the source of illumination. The interactions between the electrons and the atoms in the sample produce various signals that contain information about the sample's surface topography and composition. For example, secondary electron detectors, collecting particles emitted by atoms excited by the main beam, are typically used to observe the topography of the sample, while backscattered electron detectors show contrast depending on the atomic number.

Ion-polishing was performed with a Gatan Ilion II argon milling system. This sample preparation technique allows inducing virtually no superficial damage nor deformation as opposed to mechanical polishing. In materials that deform easily such as graphite, ion-polishing permits to observe the actual shape and size of its microstructure, including pores.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) is a crystallographic technique that uses an X-ray beam to identify the crystalline atomic structures and thus the phases present in the sample.

Phase identification by X-Ray diffraction (XRD) are performed with a Siemens D5000 diffractometer with Bragg-Brentano θ - 2θ configuration, using Cu K- α_1 radiation ($\lambda=1.54056\text{\AA}$) at room temperature. The positions of the diffraction peaks of each phase are analytically calculated from their respectively lattice and structure parameters.

In the following sections analyses performed on MoGr, including Ti dopant, CuCD and TPG are presented.

3.2. MOLYBDENUM CARBIDE – GRAPHITE

Figure 2 shows SEM observations of the perpendicular surface of a polished MG-6541Fc sample. The polished surface displays a connected graphite matrix with dispersed molybdenum carbide particles having an average size of 5 μm .

The image exhibits a good degree of compaction: most of the visible pores are simply due to the preparation of the specimens; in fact, image analysis of ion-polished surfaces reveals less than 0.5% volume of voids (Figure 3). Figure 4 shows how the ion polishing was performed.

Material properties such as bending strength and thermal conductivity (see chapter 4) suggest a strong carbide-graphite bond. The carbides not only connect the original graphite particles along the in-plane direction, but also limit the graphite delamination by connecting edges of graphite crystallites on several layers, significantly improving also the strength and the transport properties in the perpendicular direction with respect to pure, highly oriented graphite. The in-plane properties are those typical of a highly graphitized matrix, *i.e.* very high thermal and electrical conductivities, low thermal expansion coefficient and good mechanical strength.

Figure 2 - SEM of polished through-plane surface, grade MG-6541Fc. Graphite basal planes are oriented horizontally.

Figure 3 - Ion-polished surface of MG-6403Fc. Note the graphitic planes oriented vertically in the image

Figure 4 – SEM view of the ion polished material and the titanium blade used for the process. The blade is used as a flat mask to obtain better surface flatness on the polished surface.

The anisotropy of the material is noticeable when comparing in-plane and through-plane polished surfaces (Figure 5). When the in-plane surface is polished, weakly transversely bonded graphite particles can be easily removed, contrarily to the perpendicular surface, where much stronger basal plane connections exist, generating a rougher appearance.

Figure 5 - MoGr samples polished for SEM observation, showing differences in light reflectivity/scattering between in-plane (//) and through-plane (⊥) surfaces.

Titanium addition

The molybdenum carbides formed from the eutectic Mo-C liquid, experience three changes of phase until complete cool-down at room temperature (RT), as shown in the Mo-C binary diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Molybdenum – carbon diagram.

The various phases of the molybdenum carbide family have different densities, which can cause volume changes and hence cracks during phase transitions. Beam impact scenarios could locally raise the temperature of collimator absorber materials to thousands of degrees, triggering undesired phase changes. The presence of strongly stabilized phases also usually improves the radiation resistance [24].

The addition of a small quantity of titanium stabilizes down to RT the face centred cubic (FCC) α - MoC_{1-x} phase, which, in undoped carbides, is stable only at temperatures higher than 1960 °C (Figure 6). XRD tests performed at room temperature (Figure 7) confirm the presence of this cubic carbide. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis performed with SEM showed that the titanium is present only inside the carbide particles and not inside the graphite matrix. The titanium thus behaves as a dopant inside the structure of the carbides.

Apart from carbide peaks, all grades show graphite peaks corresponding to very high levels of graphitization, matching the positions of the ideal graphite structure ($a = 2.4617 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.7106 \text{ \AA}$).

Figure 7 - XRD comparison of a grade without Ti (MG-6530Aa) with another with it (MG-6541Aa). Grade MG-6541Fc is expected to give similar results to MG-6541Aa.

3.3. COPPER – DIAMOND

The micrographs of Figure 8 were obtained from the last grade developed by RHP-Technology, on the pressing face (no copper cladding). They have mono-modal diamonds of around 100µm of particle size. The faceted morphology suggest that they are artificially grown diamonds.

Figure 8 - Optical micrographs of CuCD, different magnifications

Figure 9 shows that the typical height of protruding diamonds on non-cladded surfaces is around 40µm. This depends on the size of the diamonds used. In order to achieve the required low roughness for the collimators, this material needs to be cladded with a thin layer of copper that allows the block to be machined to the required tolerances.

Figure 9 - 3D reconstruction from optical microscopy

3.4. THERMAL PYROLYTIC GRAPHITE

Figure 11 and Figure 12 show SEM micrographs of TPG. When the graphite basal planes are aligned with the electron beam, and a detector placed inside the column of the SEM is used (in-lens detector), a phenomenon called *electron channelling* becomes noticeable. Channelling is the process that constraint the path of a charged particle in a crystalline solid. It produces contrast in the SEM image, depending on the actual orientation of the crystals, allowing distinguishing crystalline domains (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - A silicon crystal viewed down the 110 direction (left) and the same crystal viewed from a randomly rotated direction (right). By Knordlun - Own work, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=34199858>

Figure 11 shows the same TPG area observed with different secondary electron detectors. At the left side, the image from in-lens detector, which is much more sensitive to the channelling effect due to its orientation with respect to both the material and the electron beam, clearly shows the perfectly layered nature of the material.

Figure 11 - SEM of TPG, through-plane surface, with basal planes horizontal in the image. In-lens (left) and lateral (right) secondary electron detectors.

Due to the low coefficient of friction between graphene layers, the polishing of in-plane surfaces was not satisfactory, leaving wavy regions of graphene flakes. Other techniques such as ion-polishing and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) are being investigated to measure the grain size of TPG.

Figure 12 - SEM of TPG. In-plane surface showing polishing artefact due to the lubricity of TPG.

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4. Thermophysical and mechanical characterization of carbon-based materials

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The thermophysical and mechanical materials characterization was performed at the CERN Mechanical Measurements Laboratory (MML). MML is specialized in the measurement of mechanical (including deformations, vibrations, ground motion or modal analysis), electrical or thermal properties of materials over a very wide range of temperatures. MML activities include individual tests, data acquisition and data analysis, as well as the design, manufacturing, installation and control of different kind of sensors.

Materials characterized by MML and included in this report are recent grades of MoGr and CuCD and TPG produced by Momentive Performance Materials.

4.2. EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS

The main thermophysical and mechanical properties measured include:

- Density
- Specific heat
- Thermal diffusivity and conductivity
- Electrical conductivity
- Flexural strength
- Elastic properties

For anisotropic materials, such as MoGr, the measurements are performed on samples with different orientations, in order to derive the complete 3D model of the material. Properties are measured as a function of temperature, except for density and electrical conductivity. The results of temperature-dependent properties for the materials investigated are reported in the following sections, while electrical conductivity and density measurements are summarized in section 4.7.

4.2.1. DENSITY

Apparent density (including internal porosity) is evaluated by means of the Archimedes method, which allows to measure precisely the volume of a specimen. The volume is calculated by weighing the specimen in a precision scale first in air, then inside a liquid of known density. The density at room temperature is calculated by dividing the mass by the measured volume. This method can overestimate the density of porous materials if some liquid is absorbed during the measurement.

Figure 13: Hydrostatic scale with Sartorius YDK03 kit.

4.2.2. SPECIFIC HEAT

A Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) is used for the measurement of specific heat. A known quantity of energy is applied to the material specimen and to a reference sample, and the temperature of both is monitored with thermocouples. By knowing the two masses, the temperature change over time, and the specific heat of the reference material, it is possible to derive the specific heat of the material under characterization. This measurement can be performed over a wide range of temperatures, depending on the DSC apparatus used; the instrument available at MML can measure materials at temperatures between RT and 1650°C according to DIN 53765:1994-03 [15].

Figure 14: Differential Scanning Calorimeter Netzsch DSC Pegasus 404C.

Difficulties were found when measuring beyond 1000°C due to the oxidation of the graphitic materials and crucibles even in the presence of small amounts of oxygen (<50 ppm). Several ways to undertake this problem are currently being studied. Nevertheless, the conductivity results beyond 1000°C reported in the next pages are calculated by extrapolating the specific heat according to the following equation:

$$C_p = \frac{1}{A \cdot T - B + C \cdot T^D} Jkg^{-1}K \quad (4.1)$$

This equation is provided by the standard ASTM C781-18 [16], and is intended to describe the specific heat of POCO AXM 5Q graphite. Coefficients A, B, C and D have been chosen throughout

a function approximation process in order to reproduce the behaviour of the tested materials with a higher fidelity.

4.2.3. THERMAL DIFFUSIVITY

The measurement of thermal diffusivity is performed with a Laser Flash Apparatus (LFA, Figure 15). As described by Parker [17], a very short laser pulse is applied to one face of a material sample, with known thickness, and the temperature on the opposite face is measured with an optical pyrometer.

Figure 15: Laser Flash Apparatus Netzsch LFA427.

Figure 16 shows the typical reading of the pyrometer; the signal amplitude is proportional to the temperature. The higher the thermal diffusivity and the smaller the thickness, the shorter the time response. The thermal diffusivity is computed from the shape of the pyrometer reading. The LFA can operate under inert atmosphere up to 2000°C.

Figure 16: Pyrometer typical reading after a laser pulse at time 0s.

During the characterization campaigns, an apparatus issue affecting measurements over high diffusivity samples was revealed. The test specimens thickness is usually between 2 and 3 mm as recommended by NETZSCH and the diameter ranges between 6 and 12.7 mm, depending on the amount of material available for sampling.

Some specimens were cut with a thickness of ~5 mm, almost twice than the recommended one. Instead of being discarded, the specimens were tested and the thermal diffusivity evaluated with the Cape-Lehman model, able to correct Parker’s one by taking into account the finite pulse time duration and the heat dissipation. The results of the measurement were surprising: such a high thermal diffusivity had never been measured before over these kinds of material. Initially, the reason was supposed to be related to some of the parameters of the manufacturing process, therefore other plates were produced with the same configuration but the specimens were these times 2 mm thick. A comparison of the thermal diffusivity values at room temperature is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Measured thermal diffusivity at room temperature over a 5 mm thick specimen and over 3 thinner specimens cut out of it. Same test parameters and set-up in all the cases.

Two possible causes were considered for the problem:

- Sample heating: the thermal diffusivity of these materials exhibits an abrupt drop with increasing temperature. If the laser pulse (heat input) rises the temperature of the sample, the corresponding measured thermal diffusivity would be lower than the one at room temperature. This effect is clearly more visible for specimens with smaller mass (i. e. the thinnest ones).
- Stringent boundary condition of the model: the characteristic time corresponding to the smaller specimens is very short and comparable to the pulse duration; therefore, it is necessary to apply a correction to the model.

A series of studies combining experimental tests and numerical simulations were undertaken in order to understand the root cause of the problem and sort it out. The conclusions of this study are that in the initial test conditions, with a sample thickness of 3 mm, the model is not able to completely correct for the finite pulse duration. The solution proposed is the usage of thicker samples propitiating sufficiently long half time rises in comparison with the laser pulse duration.

4.2.4. THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

The thermal conductivity is the product of density, specific heat and thermal diffusivity. Once these properties are known, thermal conductivity as a function of temperature is calculated with the equation:

$$\lambda(T) = \kappa(T) \cdot \rho(T) \cdot c_p(T) \quad (4.2)$$

with $\lambda(T)$ thermal conductivity, $\kappa(T)$ thermal diffusivity, $\rho(T)$ density, and $c_p(T)$ the specific heat.

4.2.5. THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENT

The thermal expansion coefficient is measured with a horizontal pushrod dilatometer (Figure 18) according to ASTM E831-14 [18].

Figure 18: Horizontal pushrod dilatometer Netzsch DIL 402E.

The specimen is kept in place by a sample holder positioned inside the dilatometer furnace. The expansion is measured by a linear variable displacement transducer (LVDT) in contact with the sample through a pushrod. As the sample length changes with temperature, the LVDT core is moved, and an output signal proportional to the displacement is recorded. The dilatometer at MML can reach temperatures of 2000 °C.

This setup is also particularly helpful to detect the presence of internal stresses in the specimen. After one thermal cycle up to 2000 °C, a residual deformation after cool-down is a symptom of released internal stresses, and should ideally be as close as possible to zero for an as-received specimen. During previous campaigns performed on carbon composites in the scope of Eucard-2 [5] it was in fact observed that, during irradiation, such internal stresses are released and provoke significant deformation, and in some case fracture, to the sample. For this reason, plates made out of composites such as MoGr are now submitted to high-temperature stress-relief treatments after production, and prior to the cutting of specimens.

4.2.6. ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

Electrical conductivity is measured by two methods: the four-wire method and with the Sigmatest portable device.

The four-wire method described by ASTM C611-98(2016) [19] consists in generating a steady direct current in a specimen by two electrodes, and measuring the voltage drop between two probes at given positions. Knowing the cross-section of the specimen, the distance between the probes, the current and the voltage drop, the bulk electrical resistivity can be obtained by virtue of Ohm’s law.

$$R(\Omega) = \frac{V}{I}; \quad \rho(\Omega/m) = R \frac{A}{L} = R \frac{d1 \cdot d2}{L} \tag{4.3}$$

Figure 19: Four-wire method apparatus (left and centre) and Sigmatest device (right).

The Sigmatest is an eddy current instrument that measures the electrical conductivity of non-ferromagnetic metals based on the complex impedance of the measuring probe according to ASTM E1004-17 [20]; when the probe is approached to the material specimen, eddy currents on its surface are generated. This method measures the electrical conductivity on a layer below the tested surface of the specimen, which depends on the skin depths and thus on the frequency of the apparatus. The instrument is more precise on isotropic materials, as it measures a bulk conductivity and does not distinguish between the directions of the measured plane and the direction orthogonal to that plane. However, the tests performed at CERN showed that, with an increase of the measurement frequency up to the higher boundary of the instrument (960 kHz), a good precision is achieved for the surface conductivity of transversely isotropic materials, such as MoGr. Moreover, a measurement at the highest frequency is also more representative of the operating conditions for the material in the LHC, where the contribution to the RF impedance under beam current depends mostly on very high frequencies.

4.2.7. FLEXURAL STRENGTH

The flexural tests are performed in compliance with ASTM C651 [21] using a Zwick/Roell testing machine fitted with ceramic fixtures, as well as a furnace allowing high temperature testing. The bending force is progressively applied to the material under test until fracture occurs. The strain is measured both with strain gauges bonded to the surface of the specimen, and with an optical laser extensometer.

Figure 20: Zwick/Roell Z400 universal testing machine (left), 4-point fixture for flexural test (right).

4.2.8. ELASTIC PROPERTIES

Impact excitation technique is a method to calculate the elastic properties of a material measuring its resonance frequencies. A specimen is hit by a Dirac impulse: vibrations are captured by a microphone and its signal is analysed in the frequency domain using a spectrum analyser.

Figure 21: experimental apparatus used for the IET.

ASTM C1259-15 [22] provides the equation to calculate the Young’s Modulus as a function of the mass, sample geometry and the first flexural frequency, while the shear modulus can be calculated as

a function of the mass, geometry and first torsional frequency. From these, the Poisson's ratio can also be calculated.

The microphone output signal is represented in Figure 22 in the frequency domain.

Figure 22. Spectrogram of the microphone signal.

Due to constraint in the available material amount, the flexural samples were used for impact excitation testing. The samples dimensions are not compliant to the standard, so the equations stated by the standard cannot be directly employed. In order to obtain a more precise result, an optimization in Ansys Workbench was performed: an iterative process is used, changing the values of the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio until the frequencies calculated match the measured ones.

4.3. MOLYBDENUM CARBIDE – GRAPHITE: GRADE MG-6403Fc

Figure 23 presents the thermal expansion of an in-plane and a through-plane samples of MG-6403-Fc provided by Brevetti Bizz during the cooling segments of the measurements. The in-plane CTE of the material (yellow curve) ranges from 2.5 to 2.9 $10^{-6}K^{-1}$ all the way from room temperature to 1950 °C.

Figure 24 and Figure 25 show respectively the thermal transfer properties of MG-6403Fc and its specific heat. The figure contains two pairs of curves corresponding to the in-plane thermal conductivity and diffusivity and the perpendicular thermal conductivity and diffusivity. MG-6403Fc features a thermal conductivity almost twice as copper in the in-plane direction.

A series of flexural tests were performed over MG-6403Fc in Plane (Figure 26). The material presented average strain to rupture of 2036 $\mu m/m$, and an average strength of 82.78 MPa.

MG-6403Fc Thermal Expansion: Cooling Segments

Figure 23: Thermal expansion of a MG-6403Fc in-plane and a through-plane samples during the cooling segments.

MG-6403Fc Thermal Diffusivity and Conductivity

Figure 24. Thermal diffusivity and conductivity of an in-plane and a through-plane MG-6403Fc samples.

MG-6403Fc Specific Heat

Figure 25: Specific heat of a MG-6403Fc Sample.

MG-6403Fc In-plane Flexural Strength

Figure 26. Flexural tests performed over four MG-6403Fc in plane samples.

4.4. MOLYBDENUM CARBIDE GRAPHITE: GRADE MG-6541Fc

MG-6541Fc, also provided by Brevetti Bizz, presents a lower CTE in the in-plane direction compared to MG-6403Fc, at the price of a higher CTE in the through-plane direction, as can be appreciated in Figure 27.

MG-6541Fc Thermal Expansion: Cooling Segments

Figure 27: Thermal expansion of a MG-6541Fc in-plane and a through-plane samples during the cooling segments.

Figure 28 reports the thermal transfer properties of MG-6541Fc. The material presents the highest properties attained so far in the development process of novel materials, with a record thermal conductivity of almost 900 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹.

MG-6541Fc Thermal Diffusivity and Conductivity

Figure 28: Thermal diffusivity and conductivity of an in-plane and a through-plane MG-6541Fc samples.

MG-6541Fc Specific Heat

Figure 29: Figure 30: Specific heat of a MG-6541Fc Sample

4.5. COPPER – DIAMOND

The addition of diamond particles to a copper matrix significantly reduces the CTE of the material. Figure 31 depicts a CTE ranging from 8 to 9.5 $10^{-6} K^{-1}$, half that of pure copper.

The thermal conductivity and diffusivity of CuCD provided by RHP Technology are shown in Figure 32.

CuCD Thermal Expansion

Figure 31: Thermal expansion of a CuCD sample during the cooling segment.

CuCD Thermal Diffusivity and Conductivity

Figure 32: Thermal conductivity and diffusivity of a CuCD sample.

The bending tests over Copper Diamond depict good repeatability in terms of strength, which is around 150 MPa. On the other hand, important differences in strain to rupture were revealed by the tests.

CuCD Thermal Specific Heat

Figure 33 Figure 34: Specific heat of a CuCD Sample

Copper Diamond Flexural Tests

Figure 35. Flexural tests performed over three Copper Diamond samples

4.6. THERMAL PYROLYTIC GRAPHITE

The results of the thermophysical tests depict a highly anisotropic lattice structure. This commercially available material represents a good reference for the newly developed composites based on graphite, as its structure is highly oriented. Figure 36 shows the thermal expansion of the material in the in-plane direction. The CTE ranges from -1.1 to $0.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$, regaining positive values at around $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 37 presents the thermal expansion of TPG in the perpendicular direction. The high expansion compared to the in-plane direction should be noted.

The material presents outstanding thermal transfer properties in the direction of the planar layers, as shown in Figure 38. The thermal conductivity at room temperature exceeds $1600 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. The figure contains two curves corresponding to the in-plane thermal conductivity and the in-plane thermal diffusivity.

TPG Thermal Expansion In-Plane

Figure 36: Thermal expansion of one sample TPG sample, in-plane direction.

TPG Thermal Expansion Through-Plane

Figure 37: Thermal expansion of one sample TPG sample through-plane.

TPG Thermal Diffusivity and Conductivity In-Plane

Figure 38. Thermal conductivity and diffusivity of one TPG sample in the in-plane direction.

The bending tests over TPG in plane depict good repeatability, with a flexural strength of 25 MPa, and a strain to rupture determined with strain gages between 600 and 700 $\mu\text{m/m}$.

TPG In-plane Flexural Tests

Figure 39. Flexural tests performed over four MG-6403Fc samples.

4.7. SUMMARY OF THE THERMOPHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL RESULTS

Table 2 summarizes the characterization results of the two most promising MoGr grades, CuCD and TPG. For MoGr and TPG, properties are provided for both in-plane (parallel to graphite basal plane) and the transversal (perpendicular to the basal plane) directions.

Table 2: Characterization results summary

Name		TPG		MG- 6403Fc		MG- 6541Fc		CuCD
Direction			⊥		⊥		⊥	Isotropic
Density (g/cm ³)		2.251		2.55		2.52		5.74
Electrical conductivity (MS/m)		2.34	0.00097	0.965	0.071	1.04*	0.46*	14.16*
Thermal Diffusivity (mm ² /s)	20 ^o C	1084.2	465.5	465.5	31.3	528.7	53.8	183.8
	500 ^o C	156.6	79.4	79.4	5.9	93.1	12.1	-
Specific Heat (J/g/K)	20 ^o C	0.69		0.624		0.693		0.390
	500 ^o C	0.89		1.304		1.481		-
Thermal Conductivity (W/m/K)	20 ^o C	1683.2	740.1	740.1	49.8	899.2	64.8	412.3
	500 ^o C	313.1	263.9	263.9	19.5	345.1	13.1	-
CTE (μm/K) from RT to:	200 ^o C	-0.75	2.67	2.67	7.93	2.05	10.15	9.25
	500 ^o C	-0.47	2.87	2.87	8.86	2.25	11.23	-
	1000 ^o C	0	2.82	2.82	11.6	2.07	13.61	-
	1900 ^o C	0.5	2.76	2.76	16.3	2.76	18.50	-
Residual deformation (%)		-	0.8	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.25	0.025
Flexural Strength (MPa)		25.5	-	58.1	10	58.1	10	110
Flexural strain to rupture (μm/m)		817	-	2430	4344	2430	4344	5421

*Measurements taken with Sigmatest at the frequency of 960 kHz

4.8. DISCUSSION AND NEXT STEPS

The thermophysical characterization confirmed the advantages of MoGr with respect to a commercial solution such as TPG. Even though TPG possess exceptional thermal properties, because of its brittleness it could not be tested mechanically in the direction perpendicular to the basal planes; moreover, also in the planar direction, TPG showed a poor strain to rupture (~800 μm/m), lower than MoGr by a factor of 3. This proved the superior performance of MoGr when used in particle accelerator equipment subjected to thermal and mechanical loads. For what concerns CuCD, the material is, mechanically, even more resistant than MoGr; however, its higher density and lower heat transport properties suggest its use in components with lower particle absorption.

Moreover, compared to TPG, both CuCD and MoGr show no or very limited residual deformation after temperature cycles, indicating small internal stresses after production. This characteristic is particularly important in particle accelerators, where internal stresses can be released in operation as an effect of high thermal loads and of radiation at high fluences [24], leading to deformation and possibly failure of the component.

In terms of experimental apparatus, in the flexural tests performed at room temperature on MG-6403Fc, the strain was measured both with strain gages as well as with the help of an optical laser extensometer. The usage of strain gages will not be possible at high temperatures, and one of the objectives of this test was to gain confidence in the measuring method, to be applied in case of high-temperature measurements that are planned in the coming months. A future development of the system also includes the possibility of measuring the electrical conductivity of materials as a function of temperature.

5.Characterization of commercial carbon materials

5.1. INTRODUCTION

The materials studied in this chapter are special carbon-based products with applications for extreme conditions and key industries, some of them coming directly from R&D, available from different producers. At GSI, in the scope of this report, the following materials were investigated:

- Several isotropic polycrystalline graphites (PG) with particle sizes ranging from 1 to 20 μm from POCO Entegris (POCO ZEE) and SGL Carbon (grades R6300, R6550, R6650),
- 2D Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-fibre reinforced carbon-fibre reinforced carbon composites (CFC), with different fibre weavings as well as high temperature, infiltration and pyrolyzation treatments from SGL Carbon (grades Sigrabond Performance, Standard 12K, Standard 6K, Mechanical, Premium, Experimental Premium),
- A 3D PAN-fibre reinforced CFC from Ariane Group,
- Two graphitic foams with densities of 0.5 (FOAM) and 0.9 (HTC) g/cm^3 from POCO Entegris,
- Glassy carbon (GC) grade SIGRADUR G (1.42 g/cm^3) from HTW Hochtemperatur-Werkstoff,
- Thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG) from Momentive Performance Materials.

Investigation techniques involve Raman spectroscopy, temperature-depending laser flash analysis, indentation and three point bending tests. Raman spectroscopy is used to assess the defect density of pristine materials. Laser flash analysis provides the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity and specific heat, that are used as an input for thermo-mechanical finite element simulations. In order to evaluate the mechanical performance of the different materials, micro-indentation and impact indentation are performed at the microscale. For characterization of bulk mechanical properties, three-point bending tests are used to determine the flexural strength.

5.2. RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Raman spectroscopy is a versatile tool to characterize different allotropes of carbon. The sample is excited with monochromatic light, usually using a laser. The probing photons interact with phonons corresponding to molecular vibrations and will thereby be shifted in energy, the so-called *Stokes shift*. The intensity of the inelastic scattered light is measured spectrally with respect to the excitation wavelength. The shift in energy gives information about the vibrational modes in the system [25].

The intensity of the inelastic scattered light is characteristic for the excited sample volume. An exemplary Raman spectrum of a polycrystalline graphite is shown in Figure 40. The Raman spectrum of any graphite exhibits three distinct regions. For an excitation wavelength of 473 nm the range between 1000 and 2000 cm^{-1} includes the D-band at $\sim 1380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the G-band at $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at $\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the second order D-band [26].

For the samples investigated in this work, we are focusing solely on the (first order) D- and G-bands and their implications. Both bands can be deconvoluted into a total of 5 peaks, the two main D- and

G-peaks and three sidebands, the D2-, D3- and D4-peaks. The G-band is the main Raman fingerprint of any sp^2 -hybridized carbon and always Raman active. The D-band is only Raman active in the presence of lattice defects like vacancies, interstitials, grain boundaries or vacancies. The second order D-band is always active, even in defect-free graphite. The ratio between the intensities of the D- and the G-band, $I(D)/I(G)$, is a first approximation of the defect density of the investigated graphitic material. The intensities are extracted from the Raman spectra by subtracting a polynomial background and fitting the spectrum using Lorentzian peak profiles for the D-, D3-, D4- and G-peaks and a Gaussian peak profile for the D2-peak.

Another extracted parameter is the full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of the G-peak. The FWHM is a function of the instrument, due to the linewidth of the excitation laser and the used spectral detector, and of the material. The sample related broadening is mainly dominated by the degree of crystallinity. The larger the FWHM the poorer the degree of crystallinity characteristic for the (average) translational symmetry of the investigated sample volume.

Figure 40: Raman spectrum of a polycrystalline graphite sample as a function of wavenumber, for a 573 nm excitation, showing the first order, D- and G-band, and the second order D-band. The measured spectrum is represented in orange. The sum of all fitted peaks is represented in black.

5.3. MICROMECHANICAL TESTING

5.3.1. MICRO-INDENTATION

The calculation of hardness and elastic modulus was performed with a NanoTest Vantage indenter produced by Micro Materials using the method of Oliver and Pharr [27]. A Berkovich diamond indenter is mounted on the micro-indenter platform. This indenter is brought into contact with the sample surface. The force is linearly increased until a predetermined depth of 5 μm is reached. The resulting maximum force P_{max} is maintained for 30 s to observe the creep. The total deformation corresponds to a maximum depth, h_{max} . Subsequently the load is linearly removed, with the final

depth, h_f , corresponding to the plastic deformation of the material. Typical load-depth dependence for the isotropic graphite grade POCO ZEE is shown in Figure 41. Using the measured maximum force, P_{max} , the final depth h_f , the initial unloading slope, S , the known area constant, $c = 24.5$, and the correction factor, $\beta = 1.034$ for a Berkovich indenter, the contact area, A , (Eq. 5.1), the hardness, H , (Eq. 5.2) and the reduced Young's modulus E_r (Eq. 5.3) are calculated by the software. At least 25 measurements at different points are performed for every material to obtain a good statistics.

Figure 41: Load depth dependence for microindentation of POCO ZEE with maximum force, P_{max} , maximum and final depth, h_{max} and h_f , respectively and the initial unloading slope S

$$A = c \cdot h_f^2 \tag{5.1}$$

$$H = \frac{P_{max}}{A} \tag{5.2}$$

$$E_r = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \cdot S}{2 \cdot \beta \cdot \sqrt{A}} \tag{5.3}$$

The reduced modulus is including the information on the elastic deformations of the sample and of the indenter tip. The Young's modulus E can then be calculated with equation (5.4).

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1-\nu^2}{E} + \frac{1-\nu_i^2}{E_i} \tag{5.4}$$

5.3.2. DYNAMIC HARDNESS MEASUREMENTS

To observe the material response under high strain rates, $\dot{\epsilon}$ (in the order of 10^2 s^{-1}), a Berkovich indenter was mounted on the nano-indentation platform. It is accelerated from a distance of $7 \mu\text{m}$ with a force of 50 mN towards the sample and the depth signal related to successive penetrations and rebound resulting from a single initial impact is measured. A typical result is shown in Figure 42 (left). The dynamic hardness can be calculated using the values of the incoming velocity, v_{in} , and outgoing velocity, v_{out} , for the first impact, the residual depth h_{res} after the first impact, the area constant, $c = 24.5$, of a Berkovich indenter and the effective mass of 0.24 kg according to equation

(5.5) [28]. Additionally, the strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ is calculated by the ratio between the incoming velocity and the maximum depth, h_{max} , as shown in Eq. (5.6) [28].

$$H_{dyn} = \frac{3m(v_{in}^2 - v_{out}^2)}{2c \cdot h_{res}^3} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{v_{in}}{h_{max}} \quad (5.6)$$

Figure 42.: Temporal evolution of depth signal and velocity for a dynamic hardness measurement using single impact nanoindentation for an isotropic graphite sample (left); temporal evolution of maximum penetration depth after successive rebounds of the nanoindenter tip, fitted with an exponential decay function (right).

Furthermore an exponential decay curve (Eq. 5.7) is used to fit the time dependence of the maximum sample penetration at each elastic reflexion after an initial nano-indenter impact, as shown in Figure 42 (right). The fit allows the estimation of the damping constant k , with fitting constants A and h_0 .

$$h = A \cdot e^{-kt} + h_0 \quad (5.7)$$

5.3.3. MULTIPLE IMPULSE MEASUREMENTS AND FAILURE ANALYSIS

Similarly to the dynamic hardness measurements, a diamond cube corner indenter with a high aspect ratio is accelerated from a distance of $3 \mu\text{m}$ towards the sample. The indenter is hold in contact for 3 s and the penetration depth is measured. After each impact the indenter is moved to the initial position with a solenoid. This process is repeated for at least 75 times allowing the monitoring of the fatigue failure of materials. Failure events can be observed as sudden depth signal increase, resulting in a change of the slope of the curve. They are related to local crack formation under the impacting tip. A typical impact fatigue curve with three marked failures is shown in Figure 43. The impact number corresponding to the first failure is detected, in this case the 4th impact. A failure probability $P(f)$ is calculated for every impact by equation (6.8) [29], where n is the impact rank of the fracture event within a total sample size of N impacts .

$$P(f) = \frac{n}{N+1} \quad (5.8)$$

Figure 43: Multiple impulse fatigue test of a 2D CFC material (Experimental grade), in plane orientation of the fibre planes; failures are observed at the 4th, 15th and 60th impact

5.3.4. THREE POINT BENDING TEST

To test the flexural strength of the materials, σ_f , 3-point bending tests were conducted using an INSTRON 5944 universal testing machine (sketch shown in Figure 44). At least 5 samples of each material and orientation, with a height, h of 4 mm, a width, b of 4 mm and a distance between the support pins l of 20 mm were loaded with an increasing force F until sample failure. With help of equation (5.8) the average flexural strength can be calculated.

Figure 44: Schematic drawing of three point bending test performed on graphitic materials

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3 \cdot F \cdot l}{2 \cdot b \cdot d^2} \tag{5.3}$$

5.4. THERMO-PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION

The thermal diffusivity, from which specific heat and thermal conductivity can be derived, was measured using laser flash analysis.

All tests were performed using a Netzsch LFA 427 with a 1064 nm laser for excitation. Measurements were conducted from room temperatures up to 1526°C. For anisotropic samples, two different orientations of the material were tested. Sample orientations were defined with respect to the direction of fibre-reinforcement in CFC or the basal planes in TPG, due to the epitaxial growth during production. In the case of graphitic foams, the assignment of directions is not as straightforward. Both foams are produced by the rapid expansion of inert gas into a liquid pitch precursor. The directions are thus defined with respect to the direction of highest thermal conductivity. The two different orientations are represented in Figure 45.

Figure 45. Schematic representation of the sample orientations for orthotropic materials. The drawn planes correspond to fibre planes in CFC, graphite basal planes in TPG. For graphitic foams in-plane corresponds to the direction of highest thermal conductivity.

5.5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.5.1. STRUCTURAL INVESTIGATIONS BY RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

The measured I(D)/I(G) ratios are shown in Figure 46. For the different polycrystalline graphite of 'R' grades, the index has similar values, without a visible correlation between it and the particle size. POCO ZEE with 1 μm particle size shows the highest I(D)/I(G). Lower particle sizes lead to a general increase of grain boundary volume that is characterized by high defect density.

The different grades of 2D fibre-reinforced carbon composites exhibit a large scattering of I(D)/I(G). Experimental Premium exhibits the smallest defect density, which can be explained by additional heat treatment in order to improve the thermal and electrical conductivity of the material. Appropriate heat treatment leads to an increased graphitization of the material and a subsequent decrease of the defect density. This is especially true for the used PAN-fibres, produced from polyacrylonitrile polymer precursor. They have favourable mechanical properties but suffer from a larger quantity of defects in comparison to fibres derived from graphitic precursors like pitch or coke. All other CFC grades exhibit much larger I(D)/I(G) than the isotropic graphites. Unfortunately, there is no connection between the trend of I(D)/I(G) and the microstructural parameters of the different materials. But it should be noted that the material with the highest I(D)/I(G), Performance, is in fact the only CFC that is reinforced by non-woven fibres.

Both graphitic foams, FOAM and HTC, exhibit low values of I(D)/I(G). As the foams were developed for heat sinks for high power electronics, both materials were optimized towards high thermal conductivity having a high degree of graphitization of the filaments. This is in accordance with what can be observed also for the Premium Experimental CFC, which was also optimized by additional graphitization treatments, leading to better thermal properties and a reduction of the I(D)/I(G).

Thermal pyrolytic graphite is produced by the dissociation of hydrocarbon gases in a chemical vapour deposition process. This leads to an epitaxial growth of graphene layers with only little defect concentration. This is reflected in the lowest value of I(D)/I(G) for TPG among all of the investigated materials. Sigradur G on the other hand has by far the highest I(D)/I(G) of all investigated materials and is also the only one having a value of this ratio higher than 1. Glassy carbon is produced by the pyrolysis of resin precursors. The removal of oxygen and hydrogen from the precursor leads to the formation of a randomly interconnected network of sp² and sp³ hybridized atoms with very little long range order (hence the name "glassy").

Figure 46. Overview of the mean I(D)/I(G) values for different carbon-based materials. The different colours respond to different material classes. Red refers to isotropic polycrystalline graphite (PG), green to carbon-fibre reinforced carbon (CFC), yellow to thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG), pink to graphitic foam (Foam) and cyan to glassy carbon (GC). Errors bars are the standard deviation of 25 individually fitted Raman measurements.

The trend of the I(D)/I(G) ratio can be correlated with that of the full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of the G-peak. The G-peak FWHM is an indicator of the crystallinity of the sample. The different particle sizes of the polycrystalline graphite correlate to the FWHM of the G-peak, with increasing FWHM for lower particle sizes. With decreasing particle size, the grain boundary and filler volume ratios are increasing leading to a decrease of average crystallinity of the sample. Only the polycrystalline graphite grade R6300, with 20 µm particle size, is not following this trend.

The G-peak FWHM of the 2D CFCs has a relative narrow distribution (Figure 47). Only the Experimental Premium 2D CFC grade is deviating, having a lower FWHM (and also the smallest error bar), as it was expected from the increased graphitization of the material due to its treatment. For the composite materials, the trend of the I(D)/I(G) is not directly connected to that of the FWHM. The grade Performance has the highest I(D)/I(G) of the CFCs but not the highest FWHM.

TPG is displaying the smallest FWHM together with the graphitic foams. The high graphitization of these samples is also reflected in the small FWHM values. Sigradur G exhibited the highest I(D)/I(G) with a value twice as large as the next ranking material – the 2D CFC, Performance. This is not connected to the FWHM value for the G-band in this material, where the value of Sigradur G is comparable to that of POCO ZEE and the non-graphitized CFCs, when error bars are taken into account.

Figure 47. Overview of the mean G-peak full-width at half maximum (FWHM) values for different carbon-based materials. The different colours respond to different material classes. Red refers to isotropic polycrystalline graphite (PG), green to carbon-fibre reinforced carbon (CFC), yellow to thermal pyrolytic graphite (TPG), pink to graphitic foam (Foam) and cyan to glassy carbon (GC). Errors bars are the standard deviation of 25 individually fitted Raman measurements.

Additionally, spatially resolved Raman mappings were conducted on samples of these materials in view of the HRMT-38 FlexMat experiment. Large scale mappings on disc shapes areas with a diameter of 3.2 mm and ~1700 individual points were performed on the beam-exit surface of the samples with respect to the beam direction during the experiment. Post-irradiation characterization should give insights to possible beam-induced structural and allotropic transformations such as graphitization, amorphization, formation of nano-sized structures.

Two of those mappings are shown as an example in Figure 48 and Figure 49 for 2D CFC Performance and TPG, respectively. Both figures show an optical micrograph of the sample surface and the corresponding mapping with respect to the intensity of the G band, extracted from the individual Raman measurements. The mappings provide information about the homogeneity of the sample surface. As seen in Figure 48, the optical micrograph of the fibre plane of Performance shows a very inhomogeneous structure where one can distinguish individual fibres bundles. These features can also be identified in Raman mapping, showing that, in between the bundles of fibres, the intensity of the graphitic peak is reduced in comparison to the fibres themselves, which exhibit much higher values. On the other hand, TPG is more homogeneous.

Figure 48: Optical micrograph of the fibre plane of Performance CFC on a 4x4 mm² area (left) and qualitative I(D)/I(G) analysis of a circular area with a diameter of 3.2 mm (right), recorded in the centre of the micrograph. Black pixels indicates low values of I(D)/I(G) and white ones high values.

Figure 49.: Optical micrograph of transversal surface of TPG on a 4x4 mm² area (left) and qualitative I(D)/I(G) analysis of a circular area with a diameter of 3.2 mm (right), recorded in the centre of the micrograph. Black pixels indicates low values of I(D)/I(G) and white pixels- high values.

5.5.2. HARDNESS AND YOUNG'S MODULUS MEASUREMENT BY MICRO-INDENTATION

The results of the measurements on micro hardness and elastic modulus are shown in Figure 50 and in Figure 51, respectively.

The hardness of isotropic graphite grades shows a dependence on the grain size. POCO ZEE, having the smallest grain size (1 μm), shows the highest hardness, while SGL R6300, having a grain size of 20 μm , shows the lowest hardness. The graphite grades with grain sizes between 7 and 10 μm have intermediate hardness values. The values for the 2D CFCs have a higher standard deviation due to the composite structure. Indents on the fibre bundles are revealing larger hardness values than indents on the matrix. No trend in hardness values regarding the orientation with respect to the fibre planes can be observed. For the composite materials, the hardness is mostly lower than that of compact isotropic graphites with small grain size due to higher porosity of the graphitic matrix in the carbon composites. The 3D CFC has a higher hardness in both orientations. For this material, the surface oriented transversal to the main fibre planes shows the highest hardness of all investigated materials. The foams have the lowest hardness due to the large pores. TPG surprisingly shows no big difference between the different material orientations and a higher scattering of the measured data for the in-plane orientation.

Figure 50. Average surface hardness of the investigated graphitic materials, obtained by 5 μm deep microindentation

For the Young’s modulus no big variations among the different isotropic graphite grades can be observed, indicating no grain size dependence. All the CFC grades possess a higher Young’s modulus for the transversal orientation, which is also higher than the values for graphite. Contrary to the hardness case, the 3D CFC shows similar Young’s modulus to the 2D CFCs. This indicates that the elastic modulus of the composites is dominated for the transversal orientation by the high values corresponding to the reinforcing fibres. The foams show also clear orientation dependence. TPG exhibits similar Young’s modulus for both orientation and, as observed for the hardness, the scattering of the measured values is much higher in the transversal orientation.

Young’s moduli derived by micro-indentation for non-isotropic materials appear systematically lower compared to those measured with macroscopic techniques (see e.g. 4.2): this discrepancy shall be further investigate in the future.

Figure 51. Average Young's modulus of the investigated graphite materials obtained by 5 μm deep microindentation

5.5.3. MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR AT HIGH STRAIN RATE

The strain rates achieved during the dynamic hardness test were calculated using equation (6.6) resulting in values between 250 and 400 s⁻¹ for all the investigated materials. The results for the dynamic hardness and the damping constant are shown in Figure 52 and Figure 53, respectively.

For the isotropic graphite, the dynamic hardness is the highest for the POCO ZEE grade which has the smallest grain size. The highest values for the 2D-CFCs are measured for SGL Performance and Premium which had also the highest values for the hardness. The 3D CFC shows small differences between the orientations, but contrary to the hardness its values are not higher than the highest values for the 2D CFCs Performance and Premium. Foams are not included in this graph, as the low resistance against penetration resulted in saturation of the indenter range, leading to no meaningful results. Overall, the dynamic hardness of all investigated materials is significantly higher than the static hardness, showing the influence of elastic response of reinforcing graphite basal planes.

Figure 52: Average dynamic hardness of the investigated graphite materials measured by nano impact, using a Berkovich indenter with 30 mN and 7 μm accelerating distance

A low damping constant is connected with good elastic bouncing of the indenter on the impacted surface. For polycrystalline graphite the lowest damping constant was obtained for POCO ZEE. The damping of the 2D CFCs is lower than the damping of isotropic graphites for all grades, except the Experimental grade. The 3D CFC has a higher damping coefficient than the 2D CFC grades. For all the CFC grades the difference between the two orientations is very low. The damping of TPG is also very high which is expected due to the low dynamic hardness and repulsion of the indenter tip after the impact.

Figure 53: Average damping constant of the investigated graphite materials obtained by nano impact with a Berkovich indenter using 30 mN and 7 μm accelerating distance

5.5.4. FAILURE PROBABILITY FOR MULTIPLE IMPULSES TEST

Beam intercepting devices experience repeated thermo-mechanical loading cycles during beam exposure. To test the fatigue behaviour, the graphite materials are repeatedly impacted by a cube corner indenter. Figure 54 shows the failure probability for the multiple impulse measurements as a function of the number of cycles for the 2D and the 3D CFC and for the TPG.

Figure 54: Failure probabilities of the investigated CFC grades and TPG after repeated impact of a cube corner indenter with a distance of 3 μm and a force of 15 mN

For all the materials, a high amount of failures occurs for the first impacts. Those surviving without a failure up to the 40th impact, usually do not fail at higher impact numbers. It can be concluded that 75 impacts per position are sufficient to observe most of the failures. Most failures are observed for the SGL 6K grade and TPG in transversal orientations with high impact number failure probabilities of about 80%. Most CFC grades show higher amount of failures in transversal orientation. Only for the grades SGL Mechanical and Pyrolytic Premium both orientations are equally stable. The 3D CFC has the lowest failure probability of all the investigated CFC grades with a final failure probability of 40% in both orientations. For TPG a high anisotropy can be observed, with the in plane orientation showing the highest failure probability. The transversal orientation for this material showed few failures at all. The isotropic graphite grades showed almost no failures either and are not shown in Figure 54. The measurements of graphitic foams saturated as for the dynamic hardness measurements, leading to no meaningful results.

5.5.5. BENDING STRENGTH OF DIFFERENT GRAPHITIC MATERIALS

To test the strength of brittle materials such as graphite and carbon composites, 3 point bending tests were performed and the results are summarized in Figure 55. The flexural strength is highly dependent on the grain size, as can be observed in the results series for the isotropic graphite grades. For the 2D CFCs a dependence on the orientation is observed, with the transversal cut possessing a higher flexural strength. For both directions the highest values are achieved for the 2D Pyrolytic CFC. The flexural strength is also higher in the transversal direction than in isotropic graphite, indicating a strengthening effect of the fibres. The 3D CFC has the lowest flexural strength of all CFC materials. As expected the carbon foams show very little flexural strength due to the high porosity and low density. TPG has bending strength values lying between the foams and the other graphitic materials. Like observed for the hardness and the Young’s modulus, the data scattering is larger in the in-plane orientation than in the transversal orientation.

Figure 55. Average flexural strength of the investigated graphite materials obtained by 3-point bending tests

5.5.6. THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES

The results of the Laser Flash Analysis measurements on the investigated graphitic materials are shown in Figure 56. It is very easily seen that TPG and the CFCs exhibit the strongest anisotropy with thermal diffusivity values lower than 6 mm²/s in the in-plane orientation. Only 2D CFC Mechanical is deviating from that trend, by exhibiting a thermal diffusivity of 7.5±0.5 mm²/s. The thermal diffusivity in the transversal direction is virtually identical for all different CFC grades at ~30 mm²/s, being dominated by the heat transport along the reinforcing carbon fibres. Only Experimental

Premium is, as expected, strongly deviating from that trend. The additional heat treatment strongly increases the thermal diffusivity by almost a factor of 3 in both directions. As it was already indicated by the Raman spectroscopy analysis, the additional heat treatment leads to an increased graphitization, especially of the PAN-fibres, that leads to the increase in thermal conductivity. The 2D CFC grade, Pyrolytic Premium, exhibits the same values as the “normal” CFC grades, despite the special infiltration treatment. Additional pyrolyzation treatment, conducted at temperatures below ~1600°C, is not leading to an increased graphitization of the original material.

Figure 56. Logarithmic representation of the thermal diffusivity at room temperature for different carbon-based materials. ⊥ and // correspond to the orientation of the material as defined in Fig. 45. Isotropic samples are denoted with ○. Error Bars are calculated from the standard deviation of three independent LFA measurements of 25 shots each.

Thermal pyrolytic graphite has the highest thermal diffusivity in the transversal direction with a value larger than 1000 mm²/s and has therefore the highest anisotropy. The epitaxial growth during production results in well-aligned graphene layers and low defect density. TPG, from the point of its thermal properties, is very close to ideal graphite.

3D CFC is less orthotropic than 2D CFCs. The in-plane diffusivity is slightly larger than the transversal direction of the 2D CFC, while the transversal diffusivity is comparable to the highest diffusivity of polycrystalline graphite grades. This result hints to the fact that 3D reinforcement is preferable is resulting in a more homogeneous materials also as respect to thermal properties.

In the case of polycrystalline graphite grades, POCO ZEE exhibits the lowest thermal diffusivity, while the SGL grades, with larger particle size, have higher thermal diffusivity in the range between 60 and 80 mm²/s. In the later cases, the correlation between particle size and diffusivity is not straightforward. R6300 with a particle size of 20 μm has the lowest thermal diffusivity, while R6550 and R6650, with 10 and 7 μm particle size, have the highest thermal diffusivity. R6500 exhibits lower

diffusivity than R6550 at the same particle size. This is an indicator that the lower particle size grades are optimized towards thermal properties.

The graphitic foams (in the in-plane orientation) exhibit the second highest thermal diffusivity of all materials. The transversal diffusivity of HTC is comparable to that of the SGL polycrystalline graphite grades. The graphitic foams are produced from pitch precursors and the resulting structure is exhibiting low defect density, as indicated by the Raman results. The small density of the graphitic foams is achieved by a large interconnected pore network. Our structural investigations show that the actual “structural” part of the foam is made up of highly-graphitized filaments (of random orientation) with a local density close to that of ideal graphite. This is the reason why the foams exhibit large thermal diffusivity in combination with a smaller anisotropy in comparison to TPG for example.

Glassy carbon, Sigradur G, has the smallest thermal diffusivity. The microstructure of this material shows only very little long-range order, due to a (random) mixing of sp²- and sp³-hybridized carbon atoms., resulting in isotropic properties.

Furthermore, the temperature dependence of the thermal diffusivity of these advance carbon materials were measured. By comparison with an appropriate standard, the specific heat and, subsequently, the thermal conductivity can be extracted from those measurements. Two examples, R6650 and Experimental Premium (in transversal orientation), are shown in Figure 57 and Figure 58 respectively. It is easily seen that both the thermal diffusivity and the thermal conductivity decrease significantly from room temperature up to the final measurement temperature of 1526 and 1426 °C respectively. The thermal diffusivity decreases by 85% and the conductivity by 50% for both materials.

The temperature dependence of the specific heat for a selection of different materials is shown in Figure 59. The specific heat values and temperature dependence of all investigated carbon materials are practically identical for the shown materials. This implies that, at constant energy deposition, transient thermal stresses will only be a function of the coefficient of thermal expansion and the Young’s modulus of the material.

Figure 57: Thermal diffusivity (black), thermal conductivity (red) and specific heat (blue) as a function of temperature for the polycrystalline graphite grade R6650 extracted from LFA measurements. A single symbol represents the average value of 5 individual measurements at the specific temperature. Error bars are calculated using the standard deviation of the 5 individual measurements and are smaller than the symbol size.

Figure 58: Thermal diffusivity (black), thermal conductivity (red) and specific heat (blue) as a function of temperature for the 2D carbon fibre-reinforced carbon composite grade Experimental Premium in transversal orientation, extracted from LFA measurements. A single symbol represents the average value of 5 individual measurements at the specific temperature. Error bars are calculated using the standard deviation of the 5 individual measurements and are smaller than the symbol size.

Figure 59: Specific heat as a function of temperature for different carbon-based materials extracted from LFA measurements. All CFCs were measured in transversal sample orientation. A single symbol represents the average value of 5 individual measurements at the specific temperature. Error bars are calculated using the standard deviation of those 5 individual measurements, but are smaller than the symbol size.

6. Ultra-high vacuum characterization of carbon-based materials

6.1. INTRODUCTION

In high-energy particle accelerators, a high or ultra-high vacuum ($<10^{-9}$ mbar) environment is of paramount importance to minimize the nuclear scattering of beam particles by residual gases and guarantee beam stability and lifetime. The pumping system and therefore the pumping speed are fixed by design: in order to reach and maintain the required pressure value, the equipment installed in particle accelerators must minimize the outgassing rate, which is defined as the difference between the quantity of gas per unit time leaving the surface and the quantity of reabsorbed gases [30].

Figure 60 shows a sketch of the experimental set-up used to measure the outgassing rate.

Figure 60: Experimental set-up for outgassing measurements. Two or more stainless steel vacuum chambers are connected through seals; an aperture is present between the chamber containing the sample and the pumping side. Two pressure gauges measure the pressure on the two sides.

The outgassing rate is calculated with the following formula:

$$Q = (P_2 - P_1) * C \quad (6.1)$$

where:

- P_1 [mbar] is the pressure measured on the pumping side
- P_2 [mbar] is the pressure measured on the sample side
- C [l/s] is the effective pumping speed, which takes into account the real pumping speed and the geometry of the aperture between the two sides of the vacuum chamber

A residual gas analyser is placed near the pressure gauge P_2 to check the species outgassed by the material.

A series of tests were performed on MoGr (grade MG-6403Fc) and CuCD samples to assess their vacuum behaviour and possible methods to reduce outgassing. All the reported results refer to samples baked under vacuum for 24 h at 250 °C, without air exposure before the measurements. This procedure is applied because without the in-situ thermal treatment the water outgassing would be the dominating one [31]: its contribution would not allow qualifying and quantifying the other gases degassed by the material. The water molecules can in fact stick to the material surface because of their strong polarity.

A complementary tool useful to investigate vacuum properties of materials is the thermal desorption spectroscopy (TDS): an electrical resistance, shown in Figure 61 heats a sample of 10x10x2mm from room temperature up to 950°C with and a residual gas analyser monitors the species outgassed from the sample at each temperature. The energy provided to the sample can break the bond between the gas molecules and the surface, therefore enhancing the outgassing, or can increase the diffusion of the species toward the surface. The outcome is a temperature-dependent outgassing rate for each species, which can help understanding the relation between the gas and the materials [32].

Figure 61: Sample heating in the TDS chamber.

Another important parameter to evaluate for the vacuum material is the secondary electron yield (SEY), which is defined as the number of secondary emitted electrons per incident electron. This property, for a material adopted in hadron accelerators, should be minimized to avoid the formation of e-clouds that can induce instabilities on the beam [33]. Figure 62 shows the scheme of the experimental set-up: electrons from the gun bombard the sample and the collector captures the secondary electrons emitted from it [34].

Figure 62: SEY experimental set-up.

6.2. MOLYBDENUM CARBIDE – GRAPHITE

6.2.1. OUTGASSING BEHAVIOUR

Samples of MG-6403Fc from BrevettiBizz (Figure 63) were tested under vacuum and their behaviour was compared with other carbon-based material such as isotropic graphite (R7550P5 from SGL Carbon) and a 2D carbon-fibre-reinforced carbon (Tatsuno FS140 by Tatsuno - Japan).

Figure 63: a) MG6403Fc b) TATSUNO CFC FS140 c) SGL graphite R7550P5

Table 3 compares the specific outgassing rate² of the three materials, measured on as-received samples.

Table 3: Specific of outgassing rate of MG-6403Fc, CFC FS140 and graphite R7550P5.

Material	Specific Outgassing rate Q_s [mbar·l/s·cm ²]
MG-6403Fc	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$
CFC FS140	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Graphite R7550P5	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$

The as-received MG-6403Fc has a specific outgassing rate one order of magnitude higher than graphite and CFC. These last two materials are extensively used in accelerator components and therefore the aim with MoGr is to obtain comparable levels of outgassing.

² The specific outgassing rate is defined as the outgassing rate calculated according to equation (6.1) divided by the surface of the sample.

The gas analysis of these materials is reported in Figure 64 to investigate the reasons of this difference. In MG-6403Fc the CH₄ (amu 16) is higher, as well as the air content, as can be recognized by the presence of N₂ (amu 28) and Ar (amu 40).

Figure 64: Normalized gas analysis of the three materials after a bake-out cycle of 24h. All the ion currents, which are proportional to the partial pressure of the gases, are divided by the H₂ one (amu=2), which is usually the dominant species.

Further observations were performed by SEM. To have a good definition of the cross section of the material, a sample of MG-6403Fc was polished with Ar ion beam. Figure 65 shows that the first 5-10um of the material are damaged during the machining: these channels can be a source of air trapping. When compared with graphite, the MG-6403Fc has smaller porosities as shown in Figure 66 and Figure 67: if some air is trapped into the bulk during the compaction, which is not performed under vacuum, it is very difficult to get rid of it because of the pore channel dimension. The reason of the high air content could therefore be related either to the surface damage or to the air trapped in the bulk during the production process.

Figure 65: SEM image of MG6403Fc sample after ion polishing. The damaged area is underline by the red rectangle.

Figure 66: SEM image of MG6403Fc after ion polishing.

Figure 67: SEM image of graphite R7550P5 after ion polishing.

Different surface treatments were performed on MoGr samples to improve the outgassing performances. Among them, the CO₂ blasting increased the outgassing rate; also, both the air and CO₂ outgassing augmented. The treatment consists in a high-speed dry ice jet on the surface of the material, which quickly sublimates in the outer layer. The combined action of thermal shock and kinetic energy of CO₂ pellets detach some graphite grain. The results of this test underline the importance of the surface state of the material in its outgassing behaviour.

A diamond paste polishing was then applied on another sample of MoGr³: the SEM image in Figure 68 shows an undamaged surface. The treatment is therefore useful to eliminate the damage induced by the previous industrial machining. A vacuum test is repeated after the treatment, but the content of air does not decrease, as can be seen in Figure 69. This behaviour indicates that despite the importance of the surface state, there is air trapped in the bulk of the material, which cannot be eliminated with surface treatments.

³ The reference grade of this sample is MG6403He. This was the first attempt to perform the cold compaction under vacuum, but the as received outgassing of the material was very similar to the MG6403Fc. For this reason, the effect of the treatment on the two grade is considered the same.

Figure 68: SEM image of MoGr after diamond paste polishing. The sample is prepared with Focused Ion Beam (FIB) before taking SEM images.

Figure 69: Normalized gas analysis of MG6403He with diamond polishing after a bake-out cycle of 24h.

Another useful method to investigate the outgassing behaviour is the Thermal Desorption Spectroscopy (TDS): a small sample is heated up from room temperature to 950°C and a residual gas analyser monitors the gases released at varying temperature. If a gas molecule is chemically bound to the material, a certain energy, provided for example by a temperature increase, is necessary to desorb the gas from the material. In Figure 70 we can see the outgassing of Ar and CO₂ as a function of temperature. The CO₂ has two peaks at temperatures corresponding to the energy needed to break

its bonds, while the Ar is much lower and without sharp peaks. The air is, in fact, geometrically trapped in the porosities of the graphitic materials and therefore its desorption cannot be easily activated by a temperature increase.

Figure 70: Thermal Desorption Spectroscopy of MG6403Fc. The masses corresponding to CO₂ and Ar are monitored during the heating up of the sample from room temperature to 950°C.

The TDS does not provide information on the temperature needed to eliminate the air. Two different thermal treatments were performed on the MG-6403Fc: a vacuum firing at 950°C for 2 hours and one vacuum firing at the same temperature, but with a duration of 48 hours. As can be seen in Table 4, the longer the duration, the stronger the outgassing reduction. The effect of the treatment is more pronounced on CFC and graphite: this could be related to the bigger porosities of these materials, from which the gas desorption is easier.

Table 4: Outgassing rate decrease after different thermal treatment.

Material	Thermal treatment	Specific Outgassing rate Q_s [mbar·l/s·cm ²]	Outgassing reduction after the treatment ⁴
MG-6403Fc	2h, 950°C	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-10}$	~3
MG-6403Fc	48h, 950°C	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	~7
CFC FS140	48h, 950°C	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	~10
Graphite R7550P5	48h, 950°C	$9.1 \cdot 10^{-13}$	~14

⁴ The outgassing of the same sample is evaluated before and after the treatment.

6.2.2. SECONDARY ELECTRON YIELD

Another important parameter to evaluate for the vacuum material is the secondary electron yield (SEY), which is defined as the number of secondary emitted electrons per incident electron. This property, for a material adopted in hadron accelerators, should be minimized to avoid the formation of e-clouds that can induce instabilities on the beam. In Figure 71 and Figure 72, one can observe the SEY of graphite R7550P5 and MG-6403Fc as a function of the energy of the incident electron beam. The maximum SEY of the two materials is very similar and quite low, possibly indicating that molybdenum carbide does not play a significant role.

Figure 71: SEY of graphite R7550P5 as a function of the incident electron beam energy. The blue curve corresponds to the as-received sample: the material is then bombarded with electron beam (e.g., it is conditioned) to decrease the SEY. Courtesy of CERN, Technology Department.

Figure 72: SEY of MG6403Fc as a function of the incident electron beam energy. The blue curve corresponds to the as-received sample: the material is then bombarded with electron beam (e.g., it is conditioned) to decrease the SEY. Courtesy of CERN, Technology Department.

6.3. COPPER – DIAMOND

A sample of CuCD from RHP was vacuum tested to evaluate the outgassing rate and the gas analysis. The gas analysis of the sample in Figure 73 shows high mass contamination, possible induced by unappropriated manipulation or to the production process. For this reason, a thermal treatment at 250°C for 48h was successively performed on the sample. After the treatment, the outgassing rate in Table 5 decreases, but the contamination does not disappear completely.

Figure 73: Normalized gas analysis of CuCD-supplier #1 after a bake-out cycle of 24h and after an additional 48h treatment.

Table 5: Specific of outgassing rate of CuCD of different material supplier and with different thermal treatment.

Treatment	Q_s [mbar·l/s·cm ²]
As-received	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-10}$
250°C, 48h	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$

6.4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MoGr and CuCD are two promising materials for beam intercepting devices in particle accelerators. In order to operate in the particle accelerator UHV environment they must possess a low outgassing rate. In the development phase, our reference and target was isostatic graphite, which is widely adapted in the UHV. MG-6403Fc produced by Brevetti Bizz was vacuum tested and it was found to have an outgassing rate higher than other graphitic materials such as graphite R7550P5 or CFC. The main reason of this difference may be related either to the surface state of the material, which is damaged by machining in the first 5-10 μm, or to the bulk. After diamond paste polishing, the surface

damage was removed, but the air content and the outgassing rate were still high, pointing to a presence of residual air in the bulk. Air might have been trapped during the compression which was not under vacuum and then, due to the high compaction and small porosity of the material, may result very difficult to remove. A thermal treatment under vacuum for 48h at 950°C is beneficial, but not sufficient to reduce the air content down to the values of the reference materials. A possible solution is to perform the compression under vacuum and with a lower applied pressure, in order to allow the degassing of air. Another option is to increase the duration of the annealing cycle at 2600°C, which is performed after the sintering: the vacuum firing tests underlined that a longer duration of high-temperature treatment is beneficial.

The CuCD tested as received has a specific outgassing rate similar to the one of the as-received MoGr. The gas analysis reveals that high mass contamination affects the behaviour of the material: this aspect is not compliant with the accelerator environment because the high mass gases have a bad influence on the beam (al.). The longer bake-out at 250°C partially decreases the outgassing rate and the contamination, which is anyway still visible. The material cannot be heated up at higher temperature because of the degradation of chromium-carbide used to enhance the bonding between copper and diamond. For this reason, all the contamination sources must be eliminated at the source, with a proper handling of the material and by controlling the cleanliness of the production process.

7. Towards the characterization of metallic thin films

7.1. INTRODUCTION

The thermomechanical characterization of Mo coatings is a relevant objective. In particular, the elastic properties (*i.e.* Young's Modulus E , shear modulus G and Poisson's ratio ν) and the thermal expansion coefficient of the films are of interest. In the case of bulk materials, several techniques are available to measure the thermomechanical properties, as explained in sections 4.2.8 and 5.5.2. In the case of thin films of micrometric thickness, the available techniques are less numerous. The Micro and Nanostructured Materials Laboratory (NanoLab) of Politecnico di Milano has developed a significant experience in this area. In particular, two non-destructive characterization techniques are currently in use: Brillouin Spectroscopy (BS) and the Substrate Curvature technique (SC). This chapter describes the first attempts to exploit these techniques for the thermomechanical characterization of Mo coatings, deposited at CERN by sputtering, on both CFC and MoGr substrates. Since both techniques are relatively non-conventional, a brief account is firstly given for both of them.

7.2. BRILLOUIN SPECTROSCOPY

Brillouin Spectroscopy (BS) investigates the vibrational excitations of materials exploiting the inelastic scattering of laser light (photon-phonon interaction). The principle of the technique is analogous to that of Raman scattering: the sample is illuminated by a laser light, and the scattered light is collected and analysed. Light is predominantly scattered in an elastic way, but the scattered light also contains the outcome of inelastic scattering: weak components that underwent a frequency shift.

Brillouin spectroscopy analyses the component that was inelastically scattered by acoustic phonons, *i.e.* the type of excitations that, at longer wavelengths, become the ultrasonic waves and the acoustic waves. These acoustic excitations are probed at wavelengths that are determined by the incident light: with visible light, acoustic excitations are probed at sub-micrometric wavelengths, which typically correspond to frequencies of the order of few GHz to few tens of GHz, *i.e.* optical wavenumbers of the order of one cm^{-1} . The technique for spectral analysis must therefore be different from that exploited for Raman spectroscopy, which detects frequency shifts of thousands, or tens of thousands, GHz [36].

Since the properties of acoustic excitations depend on the mass density and the elastic properties of materials, their measurement gives access to the elastic properties of the probed materials [36]. Bulk waves are detectable only in transparent materials [37], but at the free surface of solids Surface Acoustic Waves (SAWs) also exist, whose displacement field is confined in the vicinity of the surface, and declines with depth, the decay length being close to the wavelength.

SAWs induce a dynamic corrugation of the surface (*surface ripple mechanism*), which can be detected also in metallic films: the properties of SAWs are thus accessible [38]. In particular, the sub-micrometric wavelengths allow a peculiar sensitivity to the properties of micrometric, and even sub-

micrometric, films. More details on the physical process and on the experimental apparatus can be found in [36], [39].

The outcome of Brillouin spectrometry measurements are appropriately analysed in the frame of homogeneous and linear elastic solids. In the case of isotropic media, the elastic stiffness tensor is fully described by only two independent constants, which can be taken as C_{11} and C_{44} . The detection of bulk waves and/or SAWs can give access, if the mass density is known, to the values of both constants, leading to the full elastic characterization of the investigated media, without needing an assumption about the value of Poisson's ratio, as it is typically required by indentation. The number of detectable SAWs and their properties depends, in turn, on several factors, such as the coating thickness, and the type of coating and substrate materials (i.e. their acoustic impedance). In particular, the influence of the substrate material on SAWs propagation properties is significant for sub-micrometric films (i.e. for thickness of the order of the probing wavelength), while it becomes irrelevant for films with thicknesses above a couple of micrometres.

A film can support SAWs if it is sufficiently compact and homogeneous, the latter involving both the homogeneity of properties and the flatness of the surfaces. Inhomogeneities (including irregularities of the surface) at a scale smaller than that of the probed wavelengths (i.e. ~ 500 nm) allow propagation, the inhomogeneous medium behaving as an equivalent effective homogeneous medium. If inhomogeneities are at a scale larger than that of the probed wavelengths, the properties of single homogeneous domains can be measured, with possible differences among the properties of different domains. With inhomogeneities at the same scale of the probed wavelengths, and with discontinuities, propagation simply does not occur: SAWs are not supported; only localized and non-propagating vibrational excitations can exist. Similarly, since the inelastically scattered light has small intensity, it can be detected only if it is not overwhelmed by the elastically scattered light (which is typically more intense, by several orders of magnitude). The most favourable condition is that of a specular, or almost specular, surface, such that most of the elastic scattering goes into the reflected beam, and only a smaller amount of light is elastically scattered in other directions. Roughness hinders the propagation and the detection of SAWs. A precise upper limit for the roughness value cannot be stated, because it also depends on the lateral scales of inhomogeneities. However, SAWs are typically measurable if the roughness remains below the probed wavelength of ~ 500 nm.

A first batch of Mo coatings on CFC and MoGr substrates was deposited at CERN without a specific surface preparation, maintaining the micrometric roughness defined to obtain a good coating adhesion. Attempts to perform BS measurements were however performed, because past experience in the lab showed that in some cases measurements were possible also under non-ideal conditions. The thickness of the coatings ($5 \mu\text{m}$) is such that it could be hoped that the outer surface would not fully reproduce the roughness of the substrate. In addition, with this thickness the displacement field associated to SAWs can be considered as totally confined within the film. Therefore the properties of SAWs do not depend on the nature of the substrate (CFC or MoGr). The analysis of the Brillouin scattering results can be performed irrespectively of the type of substrate: the coating behaves like a semi-infinite medium. This also means that only the Rayleigh wave exists, other types of SAWs, like Sezawa waves, are not present.

Tests were performed on Mo coatings on both CFC and MoGr substrates, exploiting a Nd:YAG continuum laser ($\lambda = 532 \text{ nm}$), at 200 mW, in the backscattering geometry, at various laser incidence angles (i.e. from 70° to 50°). The laser spot size on the sample surface was of the order of tens of micrometres. A wide frequency range (i.e. from few GHz to over 100 GHz) was explored.

All the tests gave the same results: no detectable signal from SAWs. For both substrates the amount of elastically diffused light was peculiarly high, such that (as it is known to happen when the elastic light is very strong) spurious instrumental artefacts appeared, which were easily recognizable. This outcome suggests that, despite the coating process, the roughness of the samples remains too high to allow BS measurements.

The surfaces of the samples were therefore investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Plane view images are summarized in Figure 74. As it can be seen, the lowest magnification figures reveal strong surface irregularities for both MoGr and CFC substrates (i.e. MoGr planes or CFC fibers). These irregularities are due to the substrate production process and surface finishing, and the coating replicates them. They are of the order of the beam spot size on the surface. Mo coatings are characterized by the same morphology on both MoGr and CFC substrates. Mid-magnification images show the presence of disconnected crystals. Their size, of the order of hundreds of nanometres, is clearly of the order of the laser wavelength. These features explain the absence of signal in BS spectra. The highest magnification images, in addition, reveal that these crystals are in turn formed by columnar elongated nanometric features, which are probably related to the film deposition process itself.

Figure 74: SEM images of Mo coatings on MoGr and CFC substrates.

In summary, material irregularities are found at three different scales: tens of microns, hundreds of nanometres and tens of nanometres, the first two being particularly harmful for BS measurements. Additionally, the relative lack of connection among the crystals at the hundreds of nanometres scale suggests that also the electrical conductivity, the main reason to adopt Mo coatings, might be affected.

7.3. THERMAL EXPANSION

Recently, a custom-made setup has been developed at Politecnico di Milano to measure the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) of coatings. The setup is an optical implementation of the old method of Stoney, based on the Substrate Curvature (SC) measurements; curvature is induced, during thermal ramps, by the differential expansion between the substrate and the coating. The setup exploits a small array of parallel laser beams ($\lambda = 630 \text{ nm}$) which illuminates the sample. If the sample is perfectly flat, the reflected beams remain parallel, otherwise they converge or diverge. Detection of the reflected beams by a CMOS sensor allows to measure the substrate curvature. If the properties of the substrate are known, the properties of the coating can be obtained. Namely, if the Young's modulus, the Poisson's ratio and the CTE of the substrate are known, as well as the thickness and the elastic modulus of the coating, the substrate curvature information can be converted, under the Stoney's approximation, into a thermal stress measurement, from which the CTE of the coating can be derived. More details can be found in [40]. Possible deviations from Stoney's hypotheses, such as the anisotropy of the substrate, can be taken into account.

The applicability of the method relies on the existence and detectability of reflected beams. Since the technique can operate equivalently on positive and negative curvatures, both faces of a specimen can be, and usually are, probed. If one of the faces has irregularities that diffuse light, and do not allow to identify the positions of reflected beams, the measurement is still possible on the other face.

Both CFC and MoGr samples have the surface irregularities which were discussed above, and which are also reproduced by the Mo coatings. Both Mo and substrate surfaces do not reflect the impinging laser beams, but only diffuse them forming a speckle pattern, as shown in Figure 75. Therefore, the same sample surface features discussed above do not allow the measurements by our conventional technique.

Figure 75. Left: laser beams for SC measurements reflected by a polished surface. Right: speckle pattern produced by the Mo coated surface of a MoGr sample.

7.4. POSSIBLE COUNTERMEASURES

As detailed above, the thermomechanical characterization of the Mo coating has not been achieved, due to some intrinsic properties of the samples, namely the significant roughness. The most obvious countermeasure, polishing the samples, poses some issue for the to-be-coated surface, since we expect a reduction in the subsequent coating adhesion; however, a lower surface roughness could be achieved on the uncoated surface, as shown in Figure 5, using fine diamond polishing: this option should be tested in the future.

An alternative counter measure has been tried, aiming at obtaining smoother and more reflective surfaces: the deposition of a thin silver measurement layer (about 100 nm thick). Such a thin layer, much thinner than the Mo coating, would introduce only a minor modification of the thermomechanical behaviour of the samples. The deposition has been performed with a thermal evaporator system available at Polimi laboratory, on top of both the Mo coating and the pristine CFC and MoGr substrates.

However, we did not manage to obtain an improvement of specular reflectivity. This failure is easily interpreted by the obtained morphology, shown in Figure 76. As it can be observed, we remain far from a compact uniform layer. Firstly, the Ag layer again reproduces the morphology of the underlying CFC or MoGr, or Mo. Secondly, the thin Ag layer is itself non homogeneous, but it coalesces into a multitude of nano-droplets, adding to the roughness a contribution at the tens of nanometres scale.

Probably there is some issue concerning the chemical affinity between these substrates and the Ag film, resulting in a low wettability, such that the deposited Ag vapors do not grow in the form of a homogeneous film, but instead shrink into spherical-like nanometric agglomerates.

Figure 76. Left: Thermally evaporated Ag on MoGr. Right: thermally evaporated Ag on Mo coating.

It must also be remembered that, as mentioned above, the observed structure of the coatings, with incomplete connections of crystallites at the hundreds of nanometres scale, might also adversely affect the electrical conductivity of the coatings themselves, pushing towards a tuning of the

deposition process, or a different deposition process, which might produce more compact and homogeneous coatings.

Concerning the measurement of the *CTE*, a different possibility will be explored: a development of the measurement technique. In the present implementation, the CMOS sensor detects the image formed by the discrete reflected beams. Their positions are measured, together with their gradual displacement when the temperature is varied. As shown above, the rough surface does not reflect the beams, but only forms a speckle pattern. It can be expected that also this pattern gradually evolves when the sample curvature changes, due to the temperature variations. In principle, this pattern could be exploited for the measurement of the curvature, namely by some kind of image correlation algorithm. This possibility will be explored in the next months, and its implementation will be tried, e.g. by a digital imager correlation software.

7.5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was proven, for coatings with various structures and morphologies, that the combined use of BS and SC methods can result in a complete non-destructive thermomechanical characterization of coatings. However, the optical techniques need surfaces with sufficiently low roughness, at various scales, and of sufficient reflectivity. Beside the qualitative indication that ‘the more specular the surface, the better’, a quantitative indication can be stated by comparison with the optical wavelength, of about 500 nm: the roughness should be below this value, although this indication is not a sharp one, because the lateral size of the roughness also has a role. Clearly, these requirements are not fulfilled by the tested Mo coatings on CFC and MoGr substrates, neither are they fulfilled by the substrates themselves. A simple counter measure, the evaporation of a thin Ag layer, turned out to be ineffective. Other counter measures have been identified, mainly regarding the sample surface before coating: a better surface might be obtained by either a different surface preparation, or, for testing purposes, a substrate of a different material. A different deposition process might also be considered. For the sample curvature technique, a further development of the measurement technique could also be explored. These developments will be further investigated, and hopefully implemented, in the next months.

8. Conclusions and future plans

In this report, an extensive characterization campaign of a broad range of advanced materials for applications in future particle accelerators, particularly for beam intercepting devices, was presented.

In chapter 2, the investigated materials were introduced and their main features outlined. In the following chapters, investigations performed at CERN, GSI and Polimi were thoroughly presented: in the following, we briefly resume the main findings and conclusions and provide future plans for each investigation area. In particular modification of the manufacturing process in MoGr shall be implemented and additional tests performed in the coming months.

8.1. MICROSTRUCTURAL OBSERVATIONS (CERN)

SEM and XRD analyses, presented in chapter 3, were performed on several MoGr grades, CuCD and TPG. These tools are very effective to analyse the microstructure of materials and infer some on their macroscopic properties. In particular, it was observed through XRD that the addition of small amounts of titanium to molybdenum – graphite compounds stabilizes down to room temperature a FCC phase, which, in undoped carbides, is stable only at temperatures higher than 1960 °C. Additionally, the strongly oriented structure of TPG was highlighted by secondary electron imaging, evidencing a strong electron channelling effect in between material basal planes.

In the coming months, additional observations are foreseen on other grades of MoGr and on new carbide-graphite composites currently under development.

8.2. THERMOPHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON-BASED MATERIALS (CERN)

Several MoGr grades, CuCD and TPG were tested at CERN Mechanical Measurements Laboratory (chapter 4). The thermophysical characterization confirmed the advantages of MoGr compared to commercially available materials as TPG. Even though TPG possesses exceptional thermal properties, because of its very low strength it could not be mechanically tested in the through-plane direction; moreover, in the in-plane direction, TPG showed a poor strain to rupture (~800 $\mu\text{m/m}$), lower than MoGr by a factor of 3. This proved the superior performance of MoGr when used in particle accelerator equipment subjected to thermal and mechanical loads. For what concerns CuCD, the material is, mechanically, even more resistant than MoGr; however, its higher density and lower heat transport properties suggest its use in components with lower particle absorption.

Compared to TPG, both CuCD and MoGr showed no or very limited residual deformation after temperature cycles, indicating small internal stresses after production. This feature is particularly important in particle accelerators, where internal stresses can be released in operation as an effect of high thermal loads and of particle radiation, leading to deformation and possibly failure of the component.

Future developments include the possibility of measuring electrical conductivity and mechanical strength as a function of temperature.

8.3. CHARACTERIZATION OF COMMERCIAL CARBON MATERIALS (GSI)

Investigations performed at GSI on a wide range of commercially available advanced carbon-based materials are presented in chapter 5: these include several isotropic graphite grades, 2D ex-PAN CFC grades, a 3D ex-PAN CFC, graphitic foams, glassy carbon and TPG.

Investigation techniques included Raman spectroscopy, temperature-depending laser flash analysis, micro-indentation and three point bending tests. In order to evaluate the mechanical performance of the different materials, micro-indentation and impact indentation were performed at the microscale. For characterization of bulk mechanical properties, three-point bending tests were used to determine the flexural strength.

As expected Raman spectroscopy evidences the lowest graphitic defect concentration in carbon foams and even more in TPG, while largest defects were found in Glassy Carbon. Elastic properties measured by micro-indentation appear rather low compared to macroscopic measurements, particularly for anisotropic materials: this inconsistency should be further investigated in the future.

Mechanical properties obtained by multiple impulse test and 3-point bending test confirm the superior performances of CFC, particularly 2D (in-plane), while they evidence the weak strength of TPG, especially in the through-plane direction.

TPG is found to have the highest thermal diffusivity confirming values also found at CERN.

8.4. ULTRA-HIGH VACUUM CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON-BASED MATERIALS (CERN)

UHV performance were measured at CERN on samples of MoGr and CuCD; results are presented in chapter 6. are two promising materials for beam intercepting devices in particle accelerators. Tested MoGr grades were found to have an outgassing rate higher than other graphitic materials such as graphite or CFC for use in BID. The main reason of this difference may be related either to the surface state of the material, damaged by machining in the first 5-10 μm , or to the bulk. After diamond paste polishing, the surface damage was removed, but the air content and the outgassing rate were still high, pointing to a presence of residual air in the bulk. Air might have been trapped during the compression, which was not under vacuum and then, due to the high compaction and small porosity of the material, may result very difficult to remove. A thermal treatment under vacuum for 48h at 950°C was beneficial, but not sufficient to bring air content to specification values. Modifications to the manufacturing process were therefore proposed and further tests are expected shortly.

As-received CuCD had a specific outgassing rate similar to that of as-received MoGr. The gas analysis revealed a high mass contamination affecting the UHV behaviour. The longer bake-out at 250°C partially decreased the outgassing rate and the contamination, which was anyway still detectable. All the contamination sources shall be eliminated at the source, with a proper handling of the material and by controlling the cleanliness of the production process.

8.5. TOWARDS THE CHARACTERIZATION OF METALLIC THIN FILMS (POLIMI)

Coatings with various structures and morphologies can be thermomechanically characterized by the combined use of BS and SC methods in a complete non-destructive way. However, the optical techniques need surfaces with sufficiently low roughness, at various scales, and of sufficient reflectivity. A quantitative indication can be derived by comparison with the optical wavelength, of about 500 nm: the roughness should be below this value. These requirements were not fulfilled by the Mo coatings on CFC and MoGr substrates, which were tested at Polimi and presented in chapter 7. A simple countermeasure, the evaporation of a thin Ag layer, turned out to be ineffective. Other countermeasures have been identified, mainly regarding the sample surface before coating: a better surface might be obtained by either a different surface preparation, or, for testing purposes, a substrate of a different material. A different deposition process might also be considered. For the sample curvature technique, a further development of the measurement technique could also be explored.

Based on this, in order to perform the thermomechanical characterization of the coatings by the described optical techniques, possible future plans could be:

- Surface preparation before coatings deposition, reducing roughness down to below 500 nm;
- For testing purposes, deposition of Mo coatings on a different type of substrate (e.g. very flat Si substrates easily available);
- Possible tuning of deposition process aiming at a better continuity of Mo coating;
- In case of persistent difficulties in measuring the thermal expansion coefficient, development of an alternative substrate curvature characterization procedure, by upgrading the image processing software (i.e. speckle pattern detection).

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition